

Solitary lingual neurofibroma: a rare clinical presentation

Omar Lassikri¹, Bouanani Othmane¹

Correspondence: Omar Lassikri, Moulay Youssef Hospital, Rabat, Morocco. **Email:** dr.omar.lassikri@gmail.com

¹Moulay Youssef Hospital, Rabat, Morocco.

²Faculty of Medicine, Euromed University of Fes, Fes, Morocco.

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Introduction

Lingual neurofibroma is a tumour of the peripheral nerves, which may occur as a solitary lesion or as part of neurofibromatosis. Lingual localization of neurofibromas is rare. Clinically, it presents as a lingual mass, often painless and slowly progressive, without sensory disturbances, as observed in this 40-year-old female patient. Histologically, the tumour is non-encapsulated and composed of a benign proliferation of Schwann cells, nerve fibres, and fibroblasts within a myxoid matrix. Treatment consists of complete surgical excision to prevent recurrence and malignant transformation

Conflicts of Interest: None declared

Patient Consent Statement: The authors hold full written and informed consent from the patient for the publication of this case report, including all accompanying images.